

Research Article

Comparison of Thirty Trace Elements Contents in Thyroid Tissue Adjacent to Thyroid Malignant and Benign Nodules

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Abstract

Background: Thyroid nodules (TN) are the most common endocrine disorder worldwide. Etiology and pathogenesis of thyroid benign and malignant nodules (TBN and TMN, respectively) are still not enough understood. The present study was performed to clarify the role of some trace elements (TEs) in the origination and development of TN.

Methods: Contents of TEs such as silver (Ag), aluminum (Al), boron (B), beryllium (Be), bismuth (Bi), cadmium (Cd), cerium (Ce), cobalt (Co), chromium (Cr), cesium (Cs), iron (Fe), gallium (Ga), mercury (Hg), lanthanum (La), lithium (Li), manganese (Mn), molybdenum (Mo), neodymium (Nd), nickel (Ni), lead (Pb), praseodymium (Pr), rubidium (Rb), antimony (Sb), scandium (Sc), selenium (Se), tin (Sn), thallium (Tl), uranium (U), yttrium (Y), and zinc (Zn) were prospectively evaluated in thyroid tissue adjacent to TBN (79 patients) and to TMN (41 patients). Measurements were performed using a combination of non-destructive instrumental neutron activation analysis and destructive method such as inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry. Results of the study were additionally compared with previously obtained data for the same TEs in “normal” thyroid tissue.

Results: It was found that in thyroid tissue adjacent to TMN the mass fractions of Hg, Rb, and Se are 1.61, 1.82 and 1.60 times, respectively, higher those in thyroid tissue adjacent to TBN. The common characteristics of thyroid tissue adjacent to TBN and TMN were elevated levels of Ag, Al, Co, Hg, Mo, Ni, Rb, Sb, and U, which overdrove those in “normal” thyroid approximately in 34, 2.1, 1.8, 32, 1.95, 5.2, 1.9, 1.9 and 3.6 times, respectively, as well as reduced levels of Cs and Sc, which were 38% and 78%, respectively, lower “normal” levels of these elements, and similar contents of all other TEs studied.

Conclusions: Role of TEs in etiology and pathogenesis TBN and TMN is similar and excessive accumulation of Ag, Al, Co, Hg, Mo, Ni, Rb, Sb, and U in thyroid tissue may be involved in the TN origination and development.

Keywords: Thyroid, Thyroid benign and malignant nodules, Trace elements, Neutron activation analysis, Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry

Introduction

Thyroid benign and malignant nodules (TBN and TMN, respectively) are the most common endocrine disorder worldwide. Moreover, in some parts of the world, especially those of current or former iodine deficiency, thyroid nodules (TN) are still an endemic disease [1]. Incidence of TBN and TMN has been growing steadily over the past four decades, despite the use of iodine prophylaxis in many countries [2]. Some factors causing this higher incidence of TN were described in literature [3] and analysis of these data shown intriguing links between the etiologies of TBN and TMN [2,3]. In other words, the factors contributing to increases in the incidence of TBN are the same as those contributing to increases in TMN. However, the current state of knowledge regarding TN demonstrates that the etiology and pathogenesis of TBN and TMN are still not enough understood, because there are many not adequately explored chemicals, which induced

thyroid hormone perturbations leading to these diseases.

For over 20th century, there was the dominant opinion that TN is the simple consequence of iodine deficiency [4]. However, it was found that TN is a frequent disease even in those countries and regions where the population is never exposed to iodine shortage. Moreover, it was shown that iodine excess has severe consequences on human health and associated with the presence of TN [5-8]. It was also demonstrated that besides the iodine deficiency and excess many other dietary, environmental, and occupational factors are associated with the TN incidence [3,9-11]. Among these factors a disturbance of evolutionary stable input of many trace elements (TEs) in human body after industrial revolution plays a significant role in etiology of TN [12].

Besides iodine, many other TEs have also essential physiological functions [13]. Essential or toxic (goitrogenic, mutagenic, carcinogenic) properties of TEs depend on tissue-specific need or tolerance, respectively [13]. Excessive accumulation or an imbalance of the TEs may disturb the cell functions and may result in cellular proliferation, degeneration, death, benign or malignant transformation [13-15].

In our previous studies the complex of in vivo and in vitro nuclear analytical and related methods was developed and used for the investigation of iodine and other TEs contents in the normal and pathological thyroid [16-22]. Iodine level in the normal thyroid was investigated in relation to age, gender and some non-thyroidal diseases [23,24]. After that, variations of many TEs content with age in the thyroid of males and females were studied and age- and gender-dependence of some TEs was observed [25-41]. Furthermore, a significant difference between some TEs contents in colloid goiter, thyroiditis, thyroid adenoma, and cancer in comparison with normal thyroid was demonstrated [42-51].

The present study was performed to clarify the role of some TEs in the etiology of TBN and TMN. Having this in mind, the aim of this exploratory study was to examine differences in the content of silver (Ag), aluminum (Al), boron (B), beryllium (Be), bismuth (Bi), cadmium (Cd), cerium (Ce), cobalt (Co), chromium (Cr), cesium (Cs), iron (Fe), gallium (Ga), mercury (Hg), lanthanum (La), lithium (Li), manganese (Mn), molybdenum (Mo), neodymium (Nd), nickel (Ni), lead (Pb), praseodymium (Pr), rubidium (Rb), antimony (Sb), scandium (Sc), selenium (Se), tin (Sn), thallium (Tl), uranium (U), yttrium (Y), and zinc (Zn) in thyroid tissue adjacent to TN using a combination of non-destructive instrumental neutron activation analysis with high resolution spectrometry of long-lived radionuclides (INAA-LLR) and destructive method such as inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS), and to compare the levels of these TEs in two groups of samples (tissue adjacent to TBN and TMN, respectively). Moreover, for understanding a possible role of TEs in etiology and pathogenesis of TN results of the study were compared with previously obtained data for the same TEs in "normal" thyroid tissue [42-51].

Material and Methods

All patients suffered from TBN (n=79, mean age $M \pm SD$ was 44 ± 11 years, range 22-64) and from TMN (n=41, mean age $M \pm SD$ was 46 ± 15 years, range 16-75) were hospitalized in the Head and Neck Department of the Medical Radiological Research Centre (MRRC), Obninsk. Thick-needle puncture biopsy of suspicious nodules of the thyroid was performed for every patient, to permit morphological study of thyroid tissue at these sites and to estimate their trace element contents. In all cases the diagnosis has been confirmed by clinical and morphological results obtained during studies of biopsy and resected materials. Histological conclusions for benign nodules were: 46 colloid goiter, 19 thyroid adenoma, 8 Hashimoto's thyroiditis, and 6 Riedel's Struma, whereas for thyroid malignant tumors were: 25 papillary adenocarcinomas, 8 follicular adenocarcinomas, 7 solid carcinomas, and 1 reticulosarcoma. Samples of visually intact thyroid tissue adjacent to TBN and TMN were taken from resected materials.

"Normal" thyroids for the control group samples were removed at necropsy from 105 deceased (mean age 44 ± 21 years, range 2-87), who had died suddenly. The majority of deaths were due to trauma. A histological examination in the control group was used to control the age norm conformity, as well as to confirm the absence of micro-nodules and latent cancer.

All studies were approved by the Ethical Committees of MRRC. All the procedures performed in studies involving human participants were in accordance with the ethical standards of the institutional and/or national research committee and with the 1964 Helsinki declaration and its later amendments, or with comparable ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

All tissue samples obtained from visually intact tissue adjacent to nodules were divided into two portions using a titanium scalpel to prevent contamination by TEs of stainless steel [52]. One was used for morphological study while the other was intended for TEs analysis. After the samples intended for TEs analysis were weighed, they were freeze-dried and homogenized [53].

The pounded samples weighing about 10 mg (for biopsy) and 100 mg (for resected materials) were used for TEs measurement by INAA-LLR. The content of Ag, Co, Cr, Fe, Hg, Rb, Sb, Sc, Se, and Zn were determined by INAA-LLR using a vertical channel of the Water-Water-Research nuclear reactor (Branch of Karpov Institute, Obninsk). After non-destructive INAA-LLR investigation the thyroid samples were used for ICP-MS. The samples were decomposed in autoclaves and aliquots of solutions were used to determine the Ag, Al, As, Au, B, Be, Bi, Cd, Ce, Co, Cr, Cs, Dy, Er, Eu, Ga, Gd, Hg, Ho, Ir, La, Li, Lu, Mn, Mo, Nb, Nd, Ni, Pb, Pd, Pr, Pt, Rb, Sb, Se, Sm, Sn, Tb, Te, Th, Ti, Tl, Tm, U, Y, Yb, Zn, and Zr mass fractions by ICP-MS using an ICP-MS Thermo-Fisher "X-7" Spectrometer (Thermo Electron, USA). Information detailing with the NAA-LLR and ICP-MS methods used and other details of the analysis were presented in our earlier publications concerning TE contents in human thyroid prostate and scalp hair [29,30,35,54-61].

To determine contents of the TEs by comparison with a known standard, biological synthetic standards (BSS) prepared from phenol-formaldehyde resins were used [62]. In addition to BSS, aliquots of commercial, chemically pure compounds were also used as standards. Ten sub-samples of certified reference material (CRM) IAEA H-4 (animal muscle) and five sub-samples of CRM of the Institute of Nuclear Chemistry and Technology (INCT, Warszawa, Poland) INCT-SBF-4 Soya Bean Flour, INCT-TL-1 Tea Leaves, and INCT-MPH-2 Mixed Polish Herbs were treated and analyzed in the same conditions that thyroid samples to estimate the precision and accuracy of results.

A dedicated computer program for INAA-LLR mode optimization was used [63]. All thyroid samples were prepared in duplicate, and mean values of TEs contents were used in final calculation. Mean values of TEs contents were used in final calculation for the Ag, Co, Cr, Hg, Rb, Sb, Se, and Zn mass fractions measured by INAA-LLR and ICP-MS methods. Using Microsoft Office Excel software, a summary of the statistics, including arithmetic mean, standard deviation of mean, standard error of mean, minimum and maximum values, median, percentiles with 0.025 and 0.975 levels was calculated for TEs contents in two groups of tissue adjacent to TBN and TMN. Data for "normal" thyroid were taken from our previous publications [42-51]. The difference in the results between two groups of samples "adjacent to TBN" and "adjacent to TMN", as well as between "normal" and "adjacent to TBN and TMN combined" was evaluated by the parametric Student's t-test and non-parametric Wilcoxon-Mann-Whitney U-test.

Results

Table 1 presents certain statistical parameters (arithmetic mean, standard deviation, range of individual values) of the Ag, Al, B, Be, Bi, Cd, Ce, Co, Cr, Cs, Fe, Ga, Hg, La, Li, Mn, Mo, Nd, Ni, Pb, Pr, Rb, Sb, Sc, Se, Sn, Tl, U, Y, and Zn mass fraction in thyroid intact tissue samples of two groups "adjacent to TBN" and "adjacent to TMN".

The ratios of means and the comparison of mean values of Ag, Al, B, Be, Bi, Cd, Ce, Co, Cr, Cs, Fe, Ga, Hg, La, Li, Mn, Mo, Nd, Ni, Pb, Pr, Rb, Sb, Sc, Se, Sn, Tl, U, Y, and Zn mass fractions in pair of sample groups such as "adjacent to TBN" and "adjacent to TMN" is presented in Table 2.

Table 3 depicts certain statistical parameters (arithmetic mean, standard deviation, standard error of mean, minimal and maximal values, median,

percentiles with 0.025 and 0.975 levels) of the Ag, Al, B, Be, Bi, Cd, Ce, Co, Cr, Cs, Fe, Ga, Hg, La, Li, Mn, Mo, Nd, Ni, Pb, Pr, Rb, Sb, Sc, Se, Sn, Tl, U, Y, and Zn mass fraction in thyroid tissue adjacent “TTA” to TN (two groups “adjacent to TBN” and “adjacent to TMN” combined).

The ratios of means and the comparison of mean values of Ag, Al, B, Be, Bi, Cd, Ce, Co, Cr, Cs, Fe, Ga, Hg, La, Li, Mn, Mo, Nd, Ni, Pb, Pr, Rb, Sb, Sc, Se, Sn, Tl, U, Y, and Zn mass fractions in pair of sample groups such as normal thyroid tissue “NT” and “TTA” is presented in Table 4.

Table 1: Some statistical parameters of 30 trace element mass fraction (mg/kg, dry mass basis) in thyroid tissue adjacent to thyroid benign (TATBN) and malignant (TATMN) nodules

Element	TATBN			TATMN		
	M	SD	Range	M	SD	Range
Ag	0.473	0.663	0.0470-3.31	0.432	0.291	0.00790-1.00
Al	25.7	14.2	16.1-46.7	19.4	11.1	7.10-32.9
B	1.70	0.61	1.00-2.10	5.80	9.60	1.00-20.2
Be	0.00053	0.00004	0.00050-0.00055	<0.0002	-	-
Bi	0.478	0.453	0.0878-1.13	0.082	0.039	0.0427-0.136
Cd	2.46	1.49	0.608-4.17	6.83	12.5	0.059-25.5
Ce	0.488	0.938	0.0080-1.90	0.0085	0.0061	0.00490-0.0176
Co	0.0733	0.0979	0.00510-0.594	0.068	0.058	0.0152-0.205
Cr	0.614	0.650	0.0180-3.14	0.642	0.491	0.0512-1.58
Cs	0.0132	0.0058	0.00820-0.0195	0.0166	0.0057	0.0102-0.0240
Fe	217	141	41.5-620	256	133	109-752
Ga	≤0.024	-	<0.020-0.027	0.0273	0.0159	0.0100-0.0470
Hg	1.39	0.94	0.0140-4.68	2.24	1.87	0.253-7.78
La	≤0.088	-	<0.0030-0.321	0.0043	0.0029	0.00210-0.00760
Li	0.0350	0.0219	0.0175-0.0666	0.021	0.020	0.0096-0.0514
Mn	1.78	1.65	0.100-5.83	1.77	1.60	0.410-6.78
Mo	0.127	0.061	0.0542-0.199	0.199	0.060	0.129-0.270
Nd	≤0.048	-	<0.0020-0.174	0.0028	0.0029	0.00100-0.00710
Ni	1.71	1.43	0.520-3.30	2.78	1.65	1.10-4.60
Pb	0.83	0.71	0.240-1.70	0.69	0.87	0.220-2.00
Pr	≤0.017	-	<0.0010-0.0637	0.00107	0.00060	0.00051-0.00170
Rb	10.4	4.3	4.90-20.0	18.9	17.0	5.00-67.0
Sb	0.131	0.174	0.00760-0.757	0.248	0.415	0.00690-1.77
Sc	0.0058	0.0147	0.00020-0.0654	0.0059	0.0134	0.000200-0.0539
Se	1.93	0.86	0.647-4.34	3.08	1.67	0.704-6.91
Sn	0.135	0.119	0.0438-0.309	0.071	0.096	0.0126-0.214
Tl	≤0.0036	-	<0.0012-0.0095	0.0034	0.0021	0.00120-0.00600
U	0.00180	0.00098	0.00100-0.00300	0.00115	0.00092	0.000500-0.00180
Y	0.0088	0.0063	0.0030-0.0160	0.0039	0.0022	0.00230-0.00540
Zn	105	68	34.2-344	111	55	20.4-272

M – arithmetic mean, SD – standard deviation, Range – Min-Max values

Table 2: Differences between mean values (M±SEM) of 30 trace element mass fraction mass fraction (mg/kg, dry mass basis) in thyroid tissue adjacent to thyroid benign (TATBN) and malignant (TATMN) nodules

Element	Thyroid tissue adjacent to thyroid nodules				Ratio TATMN/TATBN
	TATBN	TATMN	Student's t-test p≤	U-test p	
Ag	0.473±0.130	0.432±0.067	0.783	>0.05	0.91
Al	25.7±7.1	19.4±5.6	0.518	>0.05	0.75
B	1.70±0.35	5.80±4.80	0.456	>0.05	3.41
Be	0.00053±0.00002	<0.0002	-	-	-

Bi	0.478±0.226	0.082±0.020	0.178	>0.05	0.17
Cd	2.46±0.75	6.83±6.2	0.535	>0.05	2.78
Ce	0.488±0.469	0.0085±0.0030	0.382	>0.05	0.17
Co	0.0733±0.0170	0.0680±0.0120	0.810	>0.05	0.93
Cr	0.614±0.111	0.642±0.098	0.851	>0.05	1.05
Cs	0.0132±0.0030	0.0166±0.0030	0.479	>0.05	1.26
Fe	217±24	256±26	0.283	>0.05	1.18
Ga	≤0.024	0.0273±0.0080	0.690	>0.05	-
Hg	1.39±0.16	2.24±0.37	0.043	≤0.01	1.61
La	≤0.088	0.0043±0.0020	0.361	>0.05	-
Li	0.0350±0.0110	0.0210±0.0100	0.385	≤0.01	0.60
Mn	1.78±0.36	1.77±0.40	0.976	>0.05	0.99
Mo	0.127±0.031	0.199±0.030	0.144	>0.05	1.57
Nd	≤0.048	0.0028±0.0010	0.364	>0.05	-
Ni	1.71±0.84	2.78±0.82	0.404	>0.05	1.63
Pb	0.83±0.35	0.69±0.44	0.815	>0.05	0.83
Pr	≤0.017	0.0011±0.0004	0.376	>0.05	-
Rb	10.4±0.7	18.9±3.3	0.020	≤0.01	1.82
Sb	0.131±0.030	0.248±0.085	0.205	>0.05	1.89
Sc	0.0058±0.0020	0.0059±0.0030	0.964	>0.05	1.02
Se	1.93±0.15	3.08±0.33	0.029	≤0.01	1.60
Sn	0.135±0.060	0.071±0.048	0.433	>0.05	0.53
Tl	≤0.0036	0.0034±0.0010	0.916	>0.05	-
U	0.0018±0.0005	0.0012±0.0007	0.501	>0.05	0.67
Y	0.0088±0.0030	0.0039±0.0016	0.236	>0.05	0.44
Zn	105±12	111±11	0.728	>0.05	1.06

M – arithmetic mean, SEM – standard error of mean, Statistically significant values are in **bold**.

Table 3: Some statistical parameters of 30 trace element mass fraction (mg/kg, dry mass basis) in in thyroid tissue adjacent (TTA) to thyroid benign and malignant nodules (combined)

Element	Mean	SD	SEM	Min	Max	Median	P 0.025	P 0.975
Ag	0.456	0.533	0.080	0.0470	3.31	0.303	0.0641	1.29
Al	22.5	12.3	4.3	7.10	46.7	19.9	8.41	44.3
B	4.04	7.14	2.70	1.00	20.2	1.00	1.00	17.5
Be	0.00052	0.00004	0.00002	0.00050	0.00055	0.000525	0.000501	0.000549
Bi	0.280	0.365	0.129	0.0427	1.13	0.112	0.0482	0.999
Cd	4.65	8.54	3.0	0.0590	25.5	1.69	0.143	21.8
Ce	0.248	0.665	0.235	0.00490	1.90	0.0109	0.00490	1.57
Co	0.071	0.083	0.011	0.00510	0.594	0.0465	0.0115	0.202
Cr	0.625	0.583	0.076	0.0180	3.14	0.483	0.0570	1.93
Cs	0.0151	0.0055	0.0020	0.00820	0.0240	0.0156	0.00850	0.0233
Fe	234	138	18	41.5	752	191	68.3	583
Ga	0.0260	0.0127	0.0050	0.0100	0.0470	0.0235	0.0113	0.0451
Hg	1.76	1.47	0.19	0.0140	7.78	1.38	0.320	5.37
La	0.052	0.119	0.045	0.00210	0.321	0.00680	0.00224	0.276
Li	0.0280	0.0209	0.0070	0.00960	0.0666	0.0207	0.00972	0.0639
Mn	1.77	1.61	0.26	0.100	6.78	1.15	0.100	5.93
Mo	0.163	0.068	0.024	0.0542	0.270	0.163	0.0638	0.261

Nd	0.025	0.060	0.021	0.00100	0.174	0.0030	0.00100	0.145
Ni	2.32	1.54	0.58	0.520	4.60	1.70	0.607	4.47
Pb	0.759	0.739	0.261	0.220	2.00	0.275	0.224	1.95
Pr	0.0103	0.0236	0.0090	0.00051	0.0637	0.00100	0.00058	0.0546
Rb	14.1	12.4	1.6	4.90	67.0	10.5	5.09	55.1
Sb	0.180	0.303	0.040	0.00690	1.77	0.0759	0.0130	0.971
Sc	0.0058	0.0141	0.0020	0.00020	0.0654	0.00020	0.00020	0.0490
Se	2.42	1.39	0.18	0.647	6.91	2.12	0.828	6.45
Sn	0.103	0.106	0.037	0.0126	0.309	0.0587	0.0148	0.292
Tl	0.0035	0.0029	0.0010	0.00120	0.00950	0.0024	0.00120	0.00889
U	0.00158	0.00093	0.00038	0.00050	0.00300	0.00140	0.00056	0.00290
Y	0.0071	0.0056	0.0023	0.00230	0.0160	0.0047	0.00239	0.0155
Zn	108	62	8.1	20.4	344	101	34.0	284

M – arithmetic mean, SD – standard deviation, SEM – standard error of mean, Min – minimum value, Max – maximum value, P 0.025 – percentile with 0.025 level, P 0.975 – percentile with 0.975 level.

Table 4: Differences between mean values (M±SEM) of 30 trace element mass fraction (mg/kg, dry mass basis) in normal thyroid (NT) and thyroid tissue adjacent to thyroid benign and malignant nodules (TTA)

Element	Thyroid tissue				Ratio
	NT	TTA	Student's t-test p≤	U-test p	TTA/NT
Ag	0.0133±0.0013	0.456±0.080	0.0000015	≤0.01	34.3
Al	10.5±1.8	22.5±4.3	0.028	≤0.01	2.14
B	0.476±0.058	4.04±2.70	0.235	>0.05	8.49
Be	0.00052±0.00008	0.00052±0.00002	0.909	>0.05	1.00
Bi	0.0072±0.0022	0.280±0.129	0.072	>0.05	3.89
Cd	2.08±0.27	4.65±3.0	0.424	>0.05	2.24
Ce	0.0080±0.0011	0.2480±0.2350	0.341	>0.05	31.0
Co	0.039±0.003	0.071±0.011	0.0054	≤0.01	1.82
Cr	0.495±0.031	0.625±0.076	0.115	>0.05	1.26
Cs	0.0245±0.0022	0.0151±0.0020	0.0045	≤0.01	0.62
Fe	222.8±9.6	234±18	0.586	>0.05	1.05
Ga	0.0316±0.0021	-	-	-	-
Hg	0.0543±0.0043	1.76±0.19	0.0000001	≤0.01	32.4
La	0.0048±0.0006	-	-	-	-
Li	0.0208±0.0022	0.0280±0.0070	0.381	>0.05	1.35
Mn	1.28±0.07	1.77±0.26	0.079	>0.05	1.38
Mo	0.0836±0.0062	0.1630±0.0240	0.012	≤0.01	1.95
Nd	0.0041±0.0004	-	-	-	-
Ni	0.449±0.046	2.32±0.58	0.018	≤0.01	5.17
Pb	0.233±0.033	0.759±0.261	0.084	>0.05	3.26
Pr	0.00107±0.00011	-	-	-	-
Rb	7.54±0.39	14.1±1.6	0.00017	≤0.01	1.87
Sb	0.0947±0.0075	0.1800±0.0400	0.040	≤0.01	1.90
Sc	0.0268±0.0060	0.0058±0.0020	0.0020	≤0.01	0.22
Se	2.22±0.14	2.42±0.18	0.363	>0.05	1.09
Sn	0.078±0.009	0.103±0.037	0.528	>0.05	1.32
Tl	0.00093±0.00007	-	-	-	-

U	0.00044±0.00006	0.00158±0.00038	0.029	≤0.01	3.59
Y	0.0026±0.0003	0.0071±0.0023	0.104	>0.05	2.73
Zn	94.8±4.2	108±8.1	0.159	>0.05	1.14

M – arithmetic mean, SEM – standard error of mean, Statistically significant values are in **bold**.

Discussion

As was shown before good agreement of the 30 TE mass fractions in CRM IAEA H-4, INCT-SBF-4, INCT-TL-1, and INCT-MPH-2 samples determined by both INAA-LLR and ICP-MS methods with the certified data of these CRMs indicates acceptable accuracy of the results obtained in the study of “adjacent to TBN”, “adjacent to TMN”, “NT”, and “TTA” groups of thyroid tissue samples presented in Tables 1-4 [29,30,35,54-61].

From Table 2, it is observed that in thyroid tissue adjacent to TMN the mass fractions of Hg, Rb, and Se are 1.61, 1.82 and 1.60 times, respectively, higher those in thyroid tissue adjacent to TBN. In a general sense Ag, Al, B, Be, Bi, Cd, Ce, Co, Cr, Cs, Fe, Ga, La, Li, Mn, Mo, Nd, Ni, Pb, Pr, Sb, Sc, Sn, Tl, U, Y, and Zn contents found in the “adjacent to TBN” and “adjacent to TMN” groups of thyroid tissue samples were similar (Table 2). It allowed combine data obtained for two groups for the purposes of finding a common TEs composition of TTA to TN and improving statistical characteristics of results for this group of samples (Table 3).

From obtained results it was found that the common characteristics of thyroid tissue adjacent to TBN and TMN were elevated levels of Ag, Al, Co, Hg, Mo, Ni, Rb, Sb, and U, which overdraw those in “normal” thyroid approximately in 34, 2.1, 1.8, 32, 1.95, 5.2, 1.9, 1.9 and 3.6 times, respectively, as well as reduced levels of Cs and Sc, which were 38% and 78%, respectively, lower “normal” levels of these elements (Table 4). Thus, if we accept the TEs contents in “normal” thyroid glands as a norm, we have to conclude that with a nodular transformation the Ag, Al, Co, Hg, Mo, Ni, Rb, Sb, and U contents in thyroid intact tissue adjacent to TN significantly increased.

Characteristically, elevated or reduced levels of TEs observed in thyroid nodules are discussed in terms of their potential role in the initiation and promotion of these thyroid lesions. In other words, using the low or high levels of the TEs in affected thyroid tissues researchers try to determine the role of the deficiency or excess of each TE in the etiology and pathogenesis of thyroid diseases. In our opinion, abnormal levels of some TEs in TN could be and cause, and also effect of thyroid tissue transformation. From the results of such kind studies, it is not always possible to decide whether the measured decrease or increase in TEs level in pathologically altered tissue is the reason for alterations or vice versa. According to our opinion, investigation of TEs contents in thyroid tissue adjacent to TN and comparison obtained results with TEs levels typical of “normal” thyroid gland may give additional useful information on the topic because these data show conditions of tissue in which TN were originated and developed.

Silver

Ag is a TE with no recognized trace metal value in the human body [64]. Food is the major intake source of Ag and this metal is authorised as a food additive (E174) in the EU [65]. Another source of Ag is contact with skin and mucosal surfaces because Ag is widely used in different applications (e.g., jewelry, wound dressings, or eye drops) [66]. Ag in metal form and inorganic Ag compounds ionize in the presence of water, body fluids or tissue exudates. The silver ion Ag⁺ is biologically active and readily interacts with proteins, amino acid residues, free anions and receptors on mammalian and eukaryotic cell membranes [67]. Besides such the adverse effects of chronic exposure to Ag as a permanent bluish-gray discoloration of the skin (argyria) or eyes (argyrosis), exposure to soluble Ag compounds may produce other toxic effects, including liver and kidney damage, irritation of the eyes, skin, respiratory, and intestinal tract, and changes in blood

cells [68]. Experimental studies shown that Ag nanoparticles may affect thyroid hormone metabolism [69]. More detailed knowledge of the Ag toxicity can lead to a better understanding of the impact on human health, including thyroid function.

Aluminum

Al is the most widely distributed metal in the environment. Environmental media may be contaminated by Al from anthropogenic sources and through the weathering of rocks and minerals [70]. The trace element Al is not described as essential, because no biochemical function has been directly connected to it. Toxic actions of Al induce oxidative stress, immunologic alterations, genotoxicity, and other disorders, including cell membrane perturbation, apoptosis, necrosis and dysplasia [70]. Furthermore, it was shown in experimental and epidemiological studies that Al can affect thyroid iodide uptake and hormones secretion [71,72]. Thus, it is possible to assume that an excessive accumulation of Al in thyroid tissue is involved in TBN and TMN etiology. Elevated level of Al in thyroid tissue adjacent to TN, observed in the present study, supports this conclusion.

Cobalt

Health effects of high Co occupational, environmental, dietary and medical exposure are characterized by a complex clinical syndrome, mainly including neurological, cardiovascular and endocrine deficits, including hypothyroidism [73,74]. Co is genotoxic and carcinogenic, mainly caused by oxidative DNA damage by reactive oxygen species, perhaps combined with inhibition of DNA repair [75]. In our previous studies it was found a significant age-related increase of Co content in female thyroid [29]. Therefore, a goitrogenic and, probably, carcinogenic effect of excessive Co level in the thyroid of old females was assumed. Elevated level of Co in thyroid tissue adjacent to TN, observed in the present study, supports this conclusion.

Mercury

In the general population, potential sources of Hg exposure include the inhalation of this metal vapor in the air, ingestion of contaminated foods and drinking water, and exposure to dental amalgam through dental care [76]. Hg is one of the most dangerous environmental pollutants [77]. The growing use of this metal in diverse areas of industry has resulted in a significant increase of environment contamination and episodes of human intoxication. Many experimental and occupational studies of Hg in different chemical states shown significant alterations in thyroid hormones metabolism and thyroid gland parenchyma [78,79]. Moreover, Hg was classified as certain or probable carcinogen by the International Agency for Research on Cancer [80]. For example, in Hg polluted area thyroid cancer incidence was almost 2 times higher than in adjacent control areas [81].

Molybdenum

Mo is an essential trace element and part of a complex called molybdenum co-factor, which is required for three mammalian enzymes—xanthine oxidase, aldehyde oxidase and sulphite oxidase [82]. Mo-dependent enzymes operate in the oxidative system of thyroid epithelial cells and also play role in the release of T3 from the thyroid gland. However, there is data that even a slight increase Mo in the diet may accelerate and/or promote the process of thyroid cell transformation, thus acting as a tumor-promoting agent rather than a carcinogen [83]. Elevated level of Mo in thyroid tissue adjacent to TN, observed in the present study, supports this statement.

Nickel

The peripheral connection between inorganic Ni and autoimmune thyroid

diseases was mentioned in the literature [84]. Moreover, well known that human exposure to highly nickel-polluted environments, such as those associated with nickel refining, electroplating, and welding, has the potential to produce not only thyroid diseases but a variety of pathologic effects. Among them are skin allergies, lung fibrosis, and cancer of the respiratory tract [85]. The exact mechanisms of nickel-induced carcinogenesis are not known. However, there is data that Ni-induced oxidative stress triggers cell proliferation, a process of great significance for cancer [86]. Thus, it is possible to assume that an excessive accumulation of Ni in thyroid tissue is involved in TBN and TMN etiology. Elevated level of Ni in thyroid tissue adjacent to TN, observed in the present study, supports this conclusion.

Rubidium

There is very little information about Rb effects on thyroid function. Rb as a monovalent cation Rb^+ is transferred through membrane by the Na^+K^+ -ATPase pump like K^+ and concentrated in the intracellular space of cells. Thus, Rb seems to be more intensively concentrated in the intracellular space of cells. The source of Rb elevated level in thyroid tissue adjacent to TN may be Rb environment overload. The excessive Rb intake may result a replacement of medium potassium by Rb, which effects on iodide transport and iodoaminoacid synthesis by thyroid [87]. The source of Rb increase in thyroid tissue adjacent to TN may be not only the excessive intake of this TE in organism from the environment, but also changed Na^+K^+ -ATPase or H^+K^+ -ATPase pump membrane transport systems for monovalent cations, which can be stimulated by endocrin system, including thyroid hormones [88]. It was found also that Rb has some function in immune response [89] and that elevated concentration of Rb could modulate proliferative responses of the cell, as was shown for bone marrow leukocytes [90]. These data partially clarify the possible role of Rb in etiology and pathogenesis of TBN and TMN.

Antimony

Evidences on the Sb-induced thyroid toxicity were recently found [91]. It was suggest that exposure to toxic metals, including Sb, even at low levels can alter gestational thyroid homeostasis [92]. Moreover, carcinogenicity data of experimental studies were concluded sufficient for Sb compounds by IARC [93]. Elevated level of Sb in thyroid tissue adjacent to TN, observed in the present study, supports these findings.

Uranium

The U accumulates in thyroid and its content is about an order of magnitude greater than the average soft tissue level [94]. In recent epidemiological study the association between environmental U exposure and the risk of thyroid cancer or other thyroid-related health effects was shown [95]. Elevated level of U in thyroid tissue adjacent to TN, observed in the present study, supports these data.

Limitations

This study has several limitations. Firstly, analytical techniques employed in this study measure only thirty TEs (Ag, Al, B, Be, Bi, Cd, Ce, Co, Cr, Cs, Fe, Ga, Hg, La, Li, Mn, Mo, Nd, Ni, Pb, Pr, Rb, Sb, Sc, Se, Sn, Tl, U, Y, and Zn) mass fractions. Future studies should be directed toward using other analytical methods which will extend the list of TEs investigated in thyroid tissue adjacent to TN. Secondly, the sample size of TBN and TMN group was relatively small and prevented investigations of TEs contents in this group using differentials like gender, functional activity of nodules, stage of disease, and dietary habits of patients with TN. Lastly, generalization of our results may be limited to Russian population. Despite these limitations, this study provides evidence on some TEs level alteration in thyroid tissue adjacent to TN and shows the necessity to continue TEs research of TN.

Conclusion

In this work, TEs analysis was carried out in the thyroid tissue adjacent to TBN and TMN using a combination of non-destructive INAA-LLR and

destructive ICP-MS methods. It was shown that this combination is an adequate analytical tool for the non-destructive determination of Ag, Al, B, Be, Bi, Cd, Ce, Co, Cr, Cs, Fe, Ga, Hg, La, Li, Mn, Mo, Nd, Ni, Pb, Pr, Rb, Sb, Sc, Se, Sn, Tl, U, Y, and Zn content in the tissue samples of human thyroid in norm and pathology. It was found that in thyroid tissue adjacent to TMN the mass fractions of Hg, Rb, and Se are 1.61, 1.82 and 1.60 times, respectively, higher those in thyroid tissue adjacent to TBN. The common characteristics of thyroid tissue adjacent to TBN and TMN were elevated levels of Ag, Al, Co, Hg, Mo, Ni, Rb, Sb, and U, which overdraw those in "normal" thyroid approximately in 34, 2.1, 1.8, 32, 1.95, 5.2, 1.9, 1.9 and 3.6 times, respectively, as well as reduced levels of Cs and Sc, which were 38% and 78%, respectively, lower "normal" levels of these elements, and similar contents of all other TEs studied. Thus, from results obtained, it was possible to conclude that the role of TEs in etiology and pathogenesis TBN and TMN is similar and excessive accumulation of Ag, Al, Co, Hg, Mo, Ni, Rb, Sb, and U in thyroid tissue may be involved in the TN origination and development.

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